

Ultrasound-assisted transesterification of *Moringa oleifera* seed oil and the effect of operating conditions on biodiesel yield

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*Transesterificación de aceite de *Moringa oleifera* asistida por ultrasonidos y efecto de condiciones de operación en el rendimiento de biodiesel*

*Transesterificació d'oli de *Moringa oleifera* assistida per ultrasons i efecte de condicions d'operació en el rendiment de biodièsel*

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ABSTRACT

due to its availability, oil content, and oil and biodiesel properties. Biodiesel production assisted by ultrasound high-frequency and low power is more sustainable and thus proves to be an alternative way to produce biodiesel. In this work, the effects of reaction time and amplitude on the *M. oleifera* oil transesterification process assisted by ultrasound were evaluated. The reaction was carried out using an ultrasonication device Hielscher Model UP200S operated at 200 W and a frequency of 24 kHz. The physicochemical properties of the *Moringa oleifera* oil were in close agreement with previous reports while the derivate methyl esters meet the ASTM D6751 and EN 14214 standards. At relatively short reaction times (5-30 min), the methyl esters yield ranged from 82.38 to 94.30 %. The results indicated that the best condition of design of experiments was achieved for 50 % of amplitude and 30 min of reaction time, obtaining the highest methyl ester yield (93.54 %). Moreover, it was also demonstrated that an increase in reaction time such as 45 min did not produce a significantly higher conversion of *Moringa oleifera* methyl esters.

Keywords: biodiesel, *Moringa oleifera*, ultrasounds, transesterification, amplitude

RESUMEN

El Aceite de *Moringa oleifera* constituye una materia prima muy prometedora para la producción de biodiesel, de debido a su disponibilidad, contenido de aceite y propiedades del biodiesel obtenido. La producción de biodiesel asistida por ultrasonidos a alta frecuencia y baja potencia es una alternativa más sostenible y efectiva para la producción de biodiesel. En el presente trabajo, se evaluó el efecto del tiempo de reacción y amplitud en la producción de biodiesel de *M. oleifera* asistida por ultrasonidos. La reacción fue llevada a cabo con un equipo de ultrasonidos Hielscher UP200S operado a 200 W y 24 kHz. Las propiedades fisicoquímicas del biodiesel fueron muy cercanas a las reportadas para este aceite y acordes a los requerimientos establecidos en las normas ASTM D6751 y EN 14214. A tiempos de reacción relativamente cortos (5-30 min), el rendimiento de metil ésteres varió entre 82,38 y 94,30 %. Los resultados indicaron que la mejor condición fue obtenida para 50 % de amplitud y 30 min de reacción, obteniéndose así el máximo rendimiento (93,54 %). También fue constatado que un incremento en el tiempo de reacción de 45 min no produce un incremento significativo de metil ésteres de *Moringa oleifera*.

Palabras clave: biodiesel, *Moringa oleifera*, ultrasonidos, transesterificación, amplitud

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RESUM:

L'Oli de *Moringa oleifera* constitueix una matèria primera molt prometedora per a la producció de biodièsel, degut a la seva disponibilitat, contingut d'oli i propietats del biodièsel obtingut. La producció de biodièsel assistida per ultrasons a alta freqüència i baixa potència és una alternativa més sostenible i efectiva per a la producció de biodièsel. En aquest treball, es va avaluar l'efecte del temps de reacció i amplitud en la producció de biodièsel de *M. oleifera* assistida per ultrasons. La reacció va ser duta a terme amb un equip d'ultrasons Hielscher UP200S operat a 200 W i 24 kHz. Les propietats fisicoquímiques del biodièsel van ser molt properes a les reportades per a aquest oli i acords als requeriments establerts a les normes ASTM D6751 i EN 14214. A temps de reacció relativament curts (5-30 min), el rendiment de metil èsters va variar entre 82,38 i 94,30%. Els resultats van indicar que la millor condició va ser obtinguda per a 50 % d'amplitud i 30 min de reacció, obtenint així el màxim rendiment (93,54 %). També va ser constatat que un increment en el temps de reacció de 45 min no produeix un increment significatiu de metil èsters de *Moringa oleifera*.

Paraules clau: biodièsel, *Moringa oleifera*, ultrasons, transesterificació, amplitud

INTRODUCTION

World fossil fuels reserves including petroleum, natural gas, and coal have been considered as the major energy resources worldwide¹, and its growing utilization has caused global warming and climate change². Consequently, emission regulations are progressively being strengthened to mitigate environmental degradation. Therefore, cleaner, and economically viable renewable energy sources are needed¹. To contribute to this critical situation, much research has been conducted to find alternatives to fossil fuels. Biofuels as alternatives to conventional fuels have been considered as a strategy that could partially address some of the environmental concerns². From this point of view, the use of biodiesel in diesel engines is advantageous over conventional diesel fuel, such as exhaust emissions reduction and better combustion properties among others³.

Biodiesel is defined as a mixture of mono-alkyl esters of long-chain fatty acids whose molecular composition is depending on the feedstock used for the fuel synthesis²⁻⁴⁻⁶. It can be obtained mainly from edibles and non-edible oils, animal fats, and algae among others. However, the use of non-edible oils as feedstock for biodiesel production has drawn more research attention as it overcomes challenges related to food security and the discussion of food versus fuel¹. Biodiesel sources should be of low production cost and have large-scale production. Certain factors that can influence the quality of biodiesel include the feedstock used, the production process, and upstream and downstream production processes. Fuel quality issues are usually reflected in the contaminants or other minor components of biodiesel.

Vegetable oils used for biodiesel production differ significantly with location according to their availability. The type of feedstock influences the quantity and quality of biodiesel produced, which could be related to its physical-chemical properties, climate conditions and soil type where the plant grows up. Soybean, palm oil, sunflower, safflower, rapeseed, coconut and peanut are the most common oils used for biodiesel production⁷. Nevertheless, in the last years, *Moringa oleifera* (*M. oleifera*) seed oil has been shown to be a promising feedstock for biodiesel production due to the availability, oil content, and the oil and biodiesel properties⁸.

Vegetable oils cannot be directly used as fuel in diesel engines because of their chemical structure and physical properties. In order to improve the properties of the oil, several methods have been studied. One of the common methods to improve the properties of vegetable oils is transesterification. After processing, vegetable oils are converted to biodiesel⁹.

Biodiesel is produced through the transesterification reaction which converts fat and oils into fatty acid alkyl ester (biodiesel) and glycerol as a co-product. This reaction also well-known as alcoholysis is the mechanism where the large, branched, triglyceride molecule present in the oils reacts with a low molecular-weight alcohol (methanol and ethanol) in the presence of a strong acid or base catalyst leading to the production of smaller, straight-chained mono-alkyl esters and glycerol. An excess of alcohol is always needed in this reversible process to favor the reaction in the forward direction. Several factors that influence the transesterification reaction are catalyst type (alkaline, acid, and enzyme), alcohol-to-oil ratio, reaction time, reaction temperature, stirring speed, moisture, and Free Fatty Acids (FFA) content in oil¹⁰.

Biodiesel production is obtained worldwide by the transesterification of triglycerides with alcohol in stirred-tank reactors mainly by alkaline homogeneous catalysts^{6,11}. One of the main challenges concerning transesterification using stirred-tank reactors is the limited speed of reaction due to the low mass transfer rates between the phases mentioned. For more stirring and effective surface contact between alcohol and oil molecules, ultrasonic waves can be used. For this reason, a method that could improve the biodiesel production process is the use of ultrasounds¹¹. Ultrasound-assisted transesterification is a very promising technique to produce biodiesel due to its cost-effectiveness and energy efficiency^{7,12}; less energy is consumed by ultrasound-assisted transesterification as compared to conventional transesterification¹³.

Several studies have demonstrated the efficiency of ultrasound compared to conventional stirring^{5,9,14-17}. Oliveira et al.⁵ explore the advantage of savings in energy consumption. The authors reported that the ultrasound method reached a similar conversion compared to the conventional method but with the significant advantage of ultrasound in reducing energy consumption. These results show that biodiesel production assisted by ultrasound high-frequency and low power is more sustainable and thus proves to be an alternative way to produce biodiesel^{5, 18, 19}.

Ultrasound produces cavitation in the reaction media (bubbles formation due to variation in pressure) which enhances the transesterification chemical reaction by providing mechanical and activation energies^{6, 13, 18, 20}. A schematic representation of the bubble's growth and behavior caused by cavitation is shown in Figure 1, including the pressure behavior, compression waves, and their effect on bubble size in time until the hot spot. In the case of the transesterification reaction between vegetable oils and methanol, the cavitation phenomenon enhances the heat transfer in the reaction media. Hence, ultrasound has successfully increased the conversion and yield, changed the reaction pathway, and/or initiated the reaction in biological, chemical, and electrochemical systems¹¹.

Figure 1. Representation of the bubble behavior caused by cavitation.

When the mixture of oil alcohol is exposed to ultrasound, ultrasonic waves generate cavitation at the exposure point²¹. As a result, an emulsion of oil and alcohol is formed that provides a large surface for the reaction, and the response time is significantly reduced. Sonochemistry is generally performed in a liquid medium. During the process, the negative pressure generated is strong enough to overcome intermolecular binding forces, and a fluid medium can be torn apart, producing tiny cavities (microbubbles). In succeeding cycles, these cavities can grow and then collapse violently with the release of large amounts of energy¹¹.

The aim of the present work is to evaluate the effect of reaction factors such as reaction time and ultrasound acoustic pressure amplitude on the *M. oleifera* methyl ester's yield when the transesterification process is assisted by ultrasound. Moreover, a comparison with conventional transesterification is also presented.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Extraction of oil from Moringa seeds

The seeds of *M. oleifera* were harvested at a facility located in Havana (23°7'0" N, 82°23'0" W), Cuba. The seeds were prepared for the extraction process, by separating firstly the kernels from the husks and drying them for 2 h at 55°C in a stove (model DHG 9146A, Shanghai Huitai Instrument Manufacturing CO., LTD, Shanghai, China) according to a previous report [22].

A lab-scale Soxhlet apparatus was used to extract the oil from the seeds using hexane as solvent (1:6 ratio during 6 h at 69°C). The solvent was separated in a rotary evaporator under vacuum (IKA RV-WerkeHB4 OS basic). Two liters of oil were collected from the extraction process.

2.2. Physical-chemical analysis and fatty acid profile of crude *M. oleifera* seed oil

Saponification value (SV), iodine value (IV), and refractive and peroxide indexes of the extracted oil were estimated using standard analytical methods²³⁻²⁵. The FFA content was determined using titration and the acid value was calculated using the method of Van Gerpen^{23, 26}. The water content was determined by Volumetric Karl Fischer Titration (ASTM E203-16).

The fatty acids content in the oil was determined by Gas Chromatography and Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis with a Gas Chromatograph (450-GC, Varian, Walnut Creek, California, USA), coupled to a Mass Spectrometer (Varian 300-MS TQ). The GC was equipped with a capillary column (Varian Factor Four) (30 m × 0.25 μm film thickness × 0.25 mm id). The injection was carried out in split mode (1:20). High-purity helium gas (99.999 %) was used as a carrier gas with a flow rate of 1 mL·min⁻¹. The oven temperature programming was as follows: initial oven temperature was held at 100°C for 1 min, then increased to 300°C at a rate of 10°C·min⁻¹ and held for 5 min. The ion source and interface temperature were set to 200°C. All the samples were analyzed in scan mode (m/z = 50-450). Additional determination of the fatty acid profile by proton nuclear magnetic resonance (1H-NMR) spectroscopy was carried out with a 400 MHz Bruker instrument. One hundred milligrams of each sample were dissolved in 500 μL of CDCl₃.

2.3 Esterification of crude *M. oleifera* seed oil

The esterification reaction is performed before transesterification to reduce the acid value of crude *M. oleifera* oil. An acid catalysis process was applied using a magnetic stirrer (yellow line MST basic C) according to a previous report²⁷. An alcohol-to-oil molar ratio (12:1) and a catalyst percentage of 1% (v/v oil) of H₂SO₄ was added to the *M. oleifera* preheated oil at 60°C for 3 h and 600 rpm of stirring speed. After that, the esterified mixture was moved to a separating funnel for 24 h to separate the treated oil (lower phase) from the upper phase (alcohol, H₂SO₄ and impurities). Subsequently, the acidity of *M. oleifera* esterified oil was measured again to corroborate the pretreatment effectiveness.

2.4 Transesterification of crude *M. oleifera* seed oil

Conventional method of *M. oleifera* oil was conducted by a standard procedure (Alkali-catalyzed transesterification) with temperature control and a magnetic stirrer operating at 500 rpm. The reaction conditions (6:1 methanol to oil molar ratio, at 60°C for 1 h, using

0.5 % of sodium hydroxide as a catalyst) were obtained by the authors in previous research²⁵. About 30 g of crude *M. oleifera* seed oil was used for each experiment. The oil was preheated before the reaction. A sodium methoxide (NaOCH₃) solution was added to the reactor. The reaction time started as soon as the catalyst/methanol solution was added to the reactor.

For ultrasound-assisted transesterification, an ultrasonication device (Hielscher Model UP200S, USA) was used for biodiesel production through transesterification. The device was operated at 200 W and had an ultrasonic frequency of 24 kHz. The amplitude and pulse are adjustable from 20 to 100 % and 0 to 100 % respectively. To carry out the transesterification reaction, methanol, and sodium hydroxide were mixed with a magnetic stirrer for 5 min to produce sodium methoxide. The produced sodium methoxide mixture was mixed with the esterified *M. oleifera* crude oil in a conical flask. The mixture was then transferred to a reaction chamber to be exposed to ultrasonic waves. A pulse of 0.3 s was adjusted while a Sonotrode Tip S14 was used. The methanol-to-oil molar ratio and sodium hydroxide concentration were 6:1 and 0.5 % (g/g oil), respectively.

2.5 Methyl esters separation and purification

After the reaction was completed, the methyl ester was kept in a separation funnel for 24 h. Then, the glycerol in the lower layer was drained out, and the methyl esters were washed with warm distilled water (5 times) until neutral pH. The washed methyl esters were dried at 110°C for 3h. The methyl ester yield (Y) was calculated through Equation (1):

$$Y(\%) = \frac{W_e}{W_o} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_e is the mass of methyl esters produced and W_o the mass of oil used in the reaction.

The physical and chemical characteristics determined included: density at 15°C (ASTM D 4052), kinematic viscosity at 40°C (ASTM D445), heating value (ASTM D240), and acid value (ASTM D664). The properties measurements were carried out in triplicate. A Herzog HVM 472 automatic viscometer operating at 40°C was used for viscosity determination whereas density was obtained through a digital densitometer Paar DMA 48. The heating value was measured with a C2000 basic IKA-combustion calorimeter.

For the cetane number (CN) estimation, an artificial neural network (ANN) model was used according to the literature report²⁴. The ANN was developed to predict the CN of biodiesel from its fatty acid composition through a back-propagation network (11:5:1) using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm.

2.6 Experimental Design and statistical analysis

The design of experiments (DoE) technique was used to develop the experimental plan required for determining the significant factors that affect the transesterification process and the best level combination that results in

the higher reaction yield²⁵. A factorial design (3²) was applied. The study was carried out with one replicate per experiment. The design included 18 experiments. The selected factors were the reaction time and the amplitude. The levels of the factors were established from reports^{9,14} and their values were coded (Table 1). The methyl esters yield was evaluated as the response variable.

Table 1. Real and codified levels for factors in the experimental design

Factor	Real value	Coded value
Reaction time (min)	5.0	-1
	17.5	0
	30.0	1
Amplitude (%)	40	-1
	50	0
	60	1

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Extraction and characterization of *M. oleifera* oil

The average oil content for the extraction process with hexane was 41.05 ± 1.25 %. The reported oil percentages are in close agreement with previous reports for diverse varieties of *M. oleifera*²⁸⁻³⁰. They ranged from 30 to 45 %²⁵. The physical-chemical properties of the extracted oil from *M. oleifera* are shown in Table 2. The results agree with reports^{27,30-35}. The main difference was detected with the *M. oleifera* Seed oil harvested from the agricultural farm of the Federal University of Agriculture Makurdi, Nigeria. Some of the physical-chemical properties for this variety such as saponification value, peroxide index, acidity, and FFA content were higher than the others. A similar result was observed for the oil acidity of *M. oleifera* from Brazil. The differences found could be due to the genetic variety of Moringa, as well as the environmental and soil conditions where they are planted.

3.2 Fatty acids content of *M. oleifera* oil

The fatty acids content was identified from the chromatogram shown in Figure 2 for each component according to the retention times.

Figure 2. *Moringa oleifera* oil chromatogram

The composition results are shown in Table 3. It could be observed that Cuban *M. oleifera*'s extracted oil shows 79.60 % content of monounsaturated fatty acids, where the oleic acid (C18:1) was the main acid representing 75.73 % (Table 3). This last result agrees with the value of the iodine index obtained as part of the physical-chemical characterization (Table 2). Iodine index values between 50 and 100 g of I/100 g of oil allowing classifying the oil as monounsaturated. The high oleic acid content of *M. oleifera* seed oil makes it highly stable, and its oxidation stability is

higher than that of polyunsaturated fatty acids such as linoleic and linolenic acids³².

Moreover, from Table 3 it is also possible to determine the total content of saturated fatty acids, corresponding to palmitic, stearic, arachidic, behenic and lignoceric; for the Cuban variety it is 17.787 %, resulting in palmitic acid being the highest percentage. The total content of saturated and monounsaturated fatty acids of Cuban *M. oleifera* oil is in close agreement with the literature reports^{28-30, 32, 33, 35, 36}. Lignoceric acid (C 24:0) was only detected in the

Table 2. Physical-chemical properties of crude *M. oleifera* oil

Property	M. oleifera varieties									
	Havana (Cuba) present work	Wild (Pakistan) ³⁰	Sindh (Pakistan) ³⁰	Periyakulam (India) ³⁰	Mbololo (Kenya) ³⁰	Wild (Malawi) ³⁰	Yunnan (China) ³²	Yunnan (China) ³³	Benue (Nigeria) ³⁴	Pernambuco (Brazil) ³⁵
Density (24°C), g·cm ⁻³	0.9004 ± 0.0002	0.9032	0.9070	0.9090	0.8800	0.8880	-	-	0.8870	0.9070 (20°C)
Refractive index (24°C)	1.4639 ± 0.0016	1.4571	1.4608	1.4570	1.4549	1.4559	-	-	1.4570	-
Iodine index, g I/100 g oil	64.77 ± 1.63	68.63	69.45	65.58	66.83	65.74	66.78	66.75	67.59	70.70
Saponification value, mg KOH·(g oil) ⁻¹	186.66 ± 1.79	181.4	186.67	188.36	178.11	184.16	189.84	182.20	218.21	179.40
Peroxide index, meq O ₂ ·(kg oil) ⁻¹	3.92 ± 0.50	1.27	0.59	1.83	1.80	0.23	7.20	1.69	5.00	5.40
Free fatty acids, % oleic acid	1.20 ± 0.02	0.81	0.40	1.12	0.85	0.82	-	-	3.16	-
Acid value, mg KOH·(g oil) ⁻¹	1.70 ± 0.17	-	-	-	-	-	2,35	0.24	6.35	20.50
Water content (mg·kg ⁻¹)	450	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	632

Table 3. Fatty acid content of *M. oleifera* oil

Fatty acid	M. oleifera varieties									
	Havana (Cuba) present work (%)	Wild (Pakistan) ³⁰	Sindh (Pakistan) ³⁰	Periyakulam (India) ³⁰	Mbololo (Kenya) ³⁰	Wild (Malawi) ³⁰	Yunnan (China) ³²	Yunnan (China) ³³	Kafrelsheikh (Egypt) ³⁶	Pernambuco (Brazil) ³⁵
Palmitic C16:0	6.017	6.450	6.500	6.460	6.040	5.510	5,430	7,800	5.90	5.80
Palmitoleic C 16:1	1.551	0.970	1.000	1.360	1.460	1.100	1,350	3,500	1.42	1.40
Stearic C 18:0	3.780	5.500	5.670	5.880	4.140	5.860	5,040	7,500	4.45	6.20
Oleic C18:1c	75.735	73.220	76.000	71.210	73.600	67.790	70,850	70,200	65.78	74.80
Linoleic C18:2 n-6	0.683	1.270	1.290	0.650	0.730	0.710	0,54	3.100	0.62	0.40
Arachidic C 20:0	2.489	4.080	3.000	3.620	2.760	3.780	-	2.000	3.21	3.70
Eicosanoic C 20:1	2.319	1.680	1.200	2.220	2.400	2.600	2,900	2,300	2.29	1.90
Behenic C 22:0	4.474	6.160	5.000	6.410	6.730	6.810	8,380	1,400	6.49	5.60
Lignoceric C 24:0	1.027	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	1.29	ND	1.36	ND
Others	1.925	0.670	0.340	2.190	2.140	5.840	4.220	2.200	8.48	0.20
Saturated	17.787	22.190	20.170	22.370	19.670	21.960	20.140	18.700	21.41	21.30
Monounsaturated	79.605	75.870	78.200	74.790	77.460	71.490	75.10	76.000	69.48	78.10
Polyunsaturated	0.683	1.270	1.290	0.650	0.730	0.710	0.540	3.100	0.62	0.40

*ND: not detected

Cuban, Egyptian and Chinese varieties, constituting the main difference. In addition, the presence of behenic acid in *M. oleifera* oil is also demonstrated, an aspect for which it is named Behen oil.

3.3 Methyl esters yield from alkali-catalyzed transesterification using magnetic stirring

Biodiesel synthesis (alkali-catalyzed transesterification) was carried out using a magnetic stirrer. The methyl esters yield obtained was 90.80 % which is in close agreement with the previous author's report²⁵. In addition, Kafuku and Mbarawa³⁷ and Chisa et al.³⁸ obtained comparable results for the transesterification process of *M. oleifera* seeds oil under similar operation parameters.

Usually, the alkali-catalyzed transesterification using magnetic stirring is limited by reaction rate (from 1 h minimum to achieve high methyl esters yield). Barnwal and Sharma³⁹ report that stirring intensity is a very important factor at the beginning of the reaction, due to feeding the reactants to the reactor a system is formed of two immiscible liquids between the oil and the alkoxide (solution alcohol/catalyst). It is also reported that high yields of methyl esters can be obtained at stirring speeds between 360 and 600 rpm. The main reason could be because speeds higher than 360 exceeds the minimum value of Reynold's number (10,000) ensuring that mass transfer of the reactants and products does not limit the reaction rate⁴⁰.

3.4 Methyl esters yield from alkali-catalyzed transesterification assisted by ultrasound

As mentioned before, transesterification using stirred-tank reactors is a challenge concerning biodiesel production as a result of the low mass transfer rates between the phases. The use of ultrasound could be a method that improves the quality of the biodiesel production process¹¹.

For biodiesel obtaining, an acid-catalyzed process was used before the transesterification reaction to reduce the acid value of crude oil. After esterification pretreatment, the acidity decreased to 0.69 % ± 0.18. This value ensures a low free fatty acid content (less than 1%) which is recommended^{41,42}, so that biodiesel can be synthesized without affecting the process performance. In addition, the water content of 450 mg·kg⁻¹ (0.045 %) was found to be lower than that of Moringa oil from Brazil (632 mg·kg⁻¹)³⁵. This result is according to oleaginous feedstock for biodiesel production (maximum of 0.1 % moisture or 1000 mg·kg⁻¹). The water content in the oils is a negative factor, helping the hydrolysis reactions, oxidation, and microbial degradation.

The response variable (methyl esters yield) obtained ranged from 82.38 % to 94.30 % (Table 4). The coded regression model was obtained and represented by Equation 2. The tests of model fit were verified to validate its quality.

Table 4. Experimental design matrix and results of the methyl esters yield

Reaction time	Amplitude	Methyl esters yield
0	-1	86.55
1	1	93.31
1	-1	90.63
-1	0	86.81
0	1	91.22
0	0	92.27
-1	-1	82.38
1	0	94.30
-1	1	87.40
1	0	91.51
-1	0	88.46
0	-1	89.44
-1	-1	84.78
1	-1	88.86
0	1	89.18
1	1	90.67
0	0	90.01
-1	1	85.63

$$Y = 90.56 + 1.2308X_1 + 2.8183X_2 - 2.2225X_1^2 \quad (2)$$

where Y is methyl esters yield, X_1 is amplitude, and X_2 is reaction time.

The statistical significance of each factor by comparing the mean square against an estimate of the experimental error may be obtained from the ANOVA for methyl esters yield, as is shown in Table 5. In this case, amplitude (0.0113), reaction time (0.0000), and amplitude interaction (0.0090) have P-values less than 0.05, indicating that they are significantly different from zero at a 95.0 % confidence level. The suitability/fit of the model was also tested using the regression equation and determination coefficient (R^2). A high value of R^2 is an indication that the fitted model can be used for prediction with good precision. The sample variation of 86.59 % for methyl esters yield might be linked to the independent variables and 13.41 % of the total variation is not explained by the model. The adjusted R^2 statistic, which is more suitable for comparing models with a different number of independent variables, was 81.00 %. The high value of the determination coefficient R^2 justified a good correlation between the independent variables. The model is suitable for the modelling and prediction of real relationships among the selected factors.

The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic tests the residuals to determine if there is any significant correlation based on the order in which they occur in the data. Since the P-value (0.6576) is greater than 5.0 %, there is no indication of serial autocorrelation in the residuals at 5.0 % of the significance level. The residuals, which are the difference between the observed values and the predicted values, should lie on a straight line in the normal probability plot. The residuals are normal and therefore the validity of the model is investigated. In addition, there is no obvious pattern from the plot of residuals versus each factor for the predicted response variable in the model. Likewise, the supposition of homogeneous

variance must be verified. A random distribution in a horizontal band of the points is obtained by plotting the predicted values against the residuals, without any clear tendency, assuring that the treatments have the same variance (Figure 3). Therefore, these three suppositions imply that the suggested model is adequate. The tests of model fit analyzed show adequate results, complying with the assumptions and applying the three basic principles of the DoE (replicates, randomization, and the use of blocks). According to the above-mentioned, the model obtained (Equation 2) can be accepted to explain the variability of the methyl ester's yield under operating conditions.

Figure 3. Residual plot for methyl ester's yield of DoE

3.5 Best condition of DoE

The three-dimensional response surface (Figure 4) is the graphical representation of the regression equation for the estimation of the best experimental condition. As the fitted model of Equation 2 brought a good estimation of the experimental conditions, it was used to predict the best possible values of the factors for obtaining maximum methyl esters yield. The best condition of DoE for both response variables was achieved for 50 % of amplitude and 30 min of reaction time, obtaining the highest methyl esters yield (93.54 %), which is based just on the analysis of the experiments developed inside the DoE, and selecting the best combination of results for both output variables simultaneously.

Figure 4. Estimated response surface of methyl ester's yield

However, due to the linear relationship observed between the reaction time factor and the methyl ester's yield (Figure 5), another experiment was developed in order to check the possibility of yield increase, with a reaction time longer than 30 min. The experiment was carried out by duplicate and a reaction time of 45 min. The amplitude was 50 % (the best factor value in the experimental design).

Figure 5. Main effects plot for methyl ester's yield (A-Yield is FAME yield vs. amplitude; R-Yield is FAME yield vs. reaction time)

The methyl ester's yields for the new experimental condition (50 % and 45 min) were 94.85 and 92.80 %. These results are close to those obtained for the best experimental design condition (50 % and 30 min) and whose values were (94.30 and 91.51 %) as is shown

Table 5. ANOVA for methyl ester's yield

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	p-Value
A: Amplitude	181.794	1	181.794	9.21	0.0113
B: Reaction time	953.160	1	953.160	48.31	0.0000
AA	197.580	1	197.580	10.02	0.0090
AB	0.2380	1	0.2380	0.12	0.7349
BB	44.100	1	44.100	2.24	0.1630
Total error	217.009	11	197.281		
Total (corr.)	161.828	17			

$R^2 = 86.5902\%$
 R^2 (adjusted for df) = 81.0028 %
 Standard Error of Est. = 1.40457
 Mean absolute error = 1.00556
 Durbin-Watson statistic = 2.35177 (P=0.6576)
 Lag 1 residual autocorrelation = - 0.257948

in Table 4. A statistical hypothesis test was made to determine if the results of the two experimental conditions abovementioned were statistically different. It is established as the null hypothesis that the difference between the yield means of both experiments was zero and the alternative hypothesis assumes that the means are different. The T-statistician was -0.198422 with a p-value of 0.7200 for 95 % confidence. Thus, the null hypothesis that supposed equal statistical means cannot be rejected. For this reason, although there is an ascending linear relationship between the reaction time factor and the methyl esters yield, a significant increase in the response variable results were not achieved for the last experimental condition (50 % and 45 min).

3.6 Comparison between magnetic stirring and ultrasounds

The highest *M. oleifera* methyl ester yield obtained from the best condition of DoE was 93.54 % during 30 min, while magnetic stirring transesterification yield was 90.80 % after 1 h. This result demonstrated the possibility to increase biodiesel production (2.74 %) and to decrease the reaction time (30 min) when the ultrasound technique is applied.

Hoseini et al.⁹ investigated *Oenothera lamarckiana* seed oil as a novel 14 feedstock for biodiesel production. An experimental design of the transesterification reaction process using ultrasonic technology was developed. The results of the research showed that the conversion of biodiesel was 92.06 % under the optimized conditions of 7.73:1 molar ratio (methanol to oil), the amplitude of 62.59 %, and 91.22 pulses for a reaction time of 9.65 min. Moreover, Koutsouki et al.¹⁴ carried out the alkaline transesterification of *Cynara cardunculus L.* seed oil with methanol for biodiesel production. The conventional transesterification reaction was studied using ultrasonication (24 kHz, without external heating) and mechanical stirring (600 rpm, 60°C). High methyl esters yield (97 %) after 20 min was obtained for conventional transesterification assisted by ultrasound. The mechanical stirring transesterification yield was 95.80 % after 1 h¹⁴. It is also reported that transesterification reaction time is much lower in a cavitation reactor as compared to the conventional stirring method^{15, 17}.

Pukale et al.¹⁷ reported for a similar reaction time that ultrasound-assisted transesterification shows a higher methyl esters yield (92 %) than the conventional stirring process (59 %). Salamatina et al.¹⁶ studied the intensifi-

cation of the biodiesel production process of vegetable oils using low-frequency ultrasonic apparatus. It was demonstrated that ultrasound intensified the biodiesel production process giving methyl esters yield of 97 % at a pulsing time of 9 s and reaction time of 30.7 min.

In consequence, the methyl ester's yield is higher when the ultrasound method is applied compared to that using mechanical stirring. Ultrasonic irradiation performs a different and more intense type of mixing than mechanical stirring¹⁴. The transesterification reaction is a mass transfer-controlled process because methanol and oil are not miscible. The intensification obtained due to ultrasonic irradiation is attributed to the physical effects of the cavitation phenomena, principally in terms of the intense levels of turbulence and mixing generated in the reactor. The effect of ultrasound, like any sound wave, alternately compresses and stretches the molecular separation of the medium through which it passes, causing a series of cycles of compression and rarefaction.

3.7 *Moringa oleifera* methyl esters

Several properties of *M. oleifera* biodiesel such as density, viscosity, acid value, cetane number (CN), and heating value were determined and compared based on Biodiesel ASTM 6751, EN 14214² and Diesel ASTM D975 standards (see Table 6). The measured physicochemical properties of *Moringa oleifera* methyl esters were in most of the cases in close agreement with literature^{2, 43} and met the biodiesel standards. Density value was lower than the requirement of ASTM D6751 but inside the range established by EN 14214. Kinematic viscosity was slightly higher compared to the maximum limit in EN 14214 standards, but inside the range of ASTM 6751. In addition, the CN was found to be slightly lower than that reported by Rashid et al.⁴⁴, but in agreement with standards. The differences found could be associated with the methods used for the measurements, but also with a threshold based on feedstock variability influencing later fuel properties. Acid value agrees with the standards and the heating value is closer but below ASTM D6751, and over the value established by EN 14214, representing an intermediate value. Nevertheless, the influence of these variations on engine performance and exhaust emissions is not an issue to be directly studied since most of the use of biodiesel for transportation is based on blends with standard diesel fuel, being biodiesel the lower content by volume in the blend.

Table 6. *Moringa oleifera* methyl ester's properties

Property	<i>M. oleifera</i> biodiesel present work	<i>M. oleifera</i> biodiesel ⁴³	<i>M. oleifera</i> ³⁸	Biodiesel ASTM D6751 ²	Biodiesel EN 14214 32 ²	Diesel fuel ASTM D975
Density at 15°C, kg·m ⁻³	870 ± 1.50	-	870	880	860-900	850
Kinematic viscosity at 40°C (mm ² ·s ⁻¹)	5.01 ± 0.36	4.85	3.23	1.9-6	3.5-5	2.6
Cetane number	56.47	-	57.90	Min. 47	Min. 51	40-55
Acid value (mg KOH·(g oil) ⁻¹)	0.30 ± 0.02	0.26	0.28	0.5 max.	0.5 max.	-
Heating value (MJ·kg ⁻¹)	40.36 ± 1.32	-	-	-	35	45.30

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the effects of reaction time and amplitude on *M. oleifera* oil transesterification process assisted by ultrasound were evaluated. Reaction was carried out using an ultrasonication device Hielscher Model UP200S operated at 200 W and a frequency of 24 kHz. The physicochemical properties of the *M. oleifera* oil were in close agreement with previous reports, while *M. oleifera* methyl esters meet the ASTM D6751 and EN 14214 standards. At relatively short reaction times (5-30 min), the *M. oleifera* methyl esters yield ranged from 82.38 to 94.30 %. The results indicated that the best condition of DOE was achieved for 50 % of amplitude and 30 min of reaction time, obtaining the highest methyl esters yield (93.54 %). Moreover, it was also demonstrated that an increase in reaction time such as 45 min did not produce a significantly higher conversion of *M. oleifera* methyl esters. The results obtained in the present work show that the ultrasound method allows a reaction time and energy saving compared with the conventional techniques.

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